

Identifying Core Research Directions for Hypercomplex Techniques in Signal and Image Processing Using Network Graph Theory

Alfredo Alcayde, Jorge Ventura and Francisco G. Montoya

Abstract

This paper aims to identify core research directions and provide a comprehensive overview of major advancements in the field of hypercomplex signal and image processing techniques using network graph theory. The methodology employs community detection algorithms on research networks to uncover relationships among researchers and topic fields in the hypercomplex domain. This is accomplished through a comprehensive academic database search and metadata analysis from pertinent papers. The work focuses on the utility of these techniques in various applications and the value of mathematically rich frameworks. The results demonstrate how optimized network-based approaches can determine common topics and emerging lines of research. The study identifies distinct core research directions, including significant advancements in image/video processing, computer vision, signal processing, security, navigation, and machine learning within the hypercomplex domain. Current trends, challenges, opportunities and the most promising directions in hypercomplex signal and image processing are highlighted based on a thorough literature analysis. This provides actionable insights for researchers to advance this domain.

Index Terms

hypercomplex signal processing, hypercomplex image processing, community detection, graph network theory

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background and Motivation

As digital technology pervades our daily lives, the importance of signal and image processing has never been greater. These fields traditionally employ complex numbers and matrix algebras to develop algorithms that can enhance, filter, or extract features from signals and images. However, an emerging topic that is increasingly drawing attention from researchers is the use of hypercomplex numbers—like quaternions or octonions—in signal and image processing. This mathematical framework offers unique advantages, including reduced computational complexity and the ability to represent higher-dimensional data more naturally. Hypercomplex numbers have found applications in various domains including color image processing, 3D transformations, and even in the design of novel machine learning algorithms tailored for complex data types. This work aims to provide a comprehensive overview of major advancements in the field of hypercomplex signal and image processing techniques., starting with foundational concepts in hypercomplex algebra and progressing to its applications in signal and image processing. We cover in an accessible style how the theoretical and computational concepts from the hypercomplex domain have been spread across different fields and subtopics, illustrating how hypercomplex numbers offer a rich and potentially transformative approach to conventional problems. We will also discuss open research challenges, practical constraints, and the future directions of this exciting field.

B. Hypercomplex Number Systems

Hypercomplex numbers are an extension of complex numbers that provide multi-dimensional representations suitable for sophisticated signal and image processing techniques. In contrast to real and complex numbers representing sets of one and two dimensions, respectively, hypercomplex number systems can represent sets of three or more dimensions. The extra dimensions allow for capturing more information and enable more efficient computations of signals and images. The most common and widely used hypercomplex number systems are quaternions \mathbb{H} , Clifford algebras $\mathcal{C}\ell_{p,q,r}$ and octonions \mathbb{O} (among others).

Compared to real and complex numbers, hypercomplex number systems have several advantages for representing and processing multidimensional signals and images. They provide a natural way to encode multiple components in a single mathematical framework and can inherently preserve important structural relationships within multidimensional data. For example, quaternions can compactly represent rotations in 3D graphics and computer vision applications. Dual quaternions can

also accomplish translations. The extra dimensions in hypercomplex systems also lead to better conditioning and numerical stability in transforms and filters. This allows more accurate processing of noisy or imperfect real-world data. Additionally, the extra degrees of freedom give more flexibility in hypercomplex filter design to achieve desired frequency responses tailored to specific applications. However, despite these promising capabilities, many areas remain less explored regarding hypercomplex signal processing. Some open questions include optimal methods for lossy compression and reconstruction of hypercomplex image data, studying the effects of common processing operations on the underlying geometric interpretations, and hypercomplex neural networks for multidimensional pattern recognition.

1) *Quaternion numbers*: Quaternions, proposed by William Hamilton in 1843, have three imaginary units and form a four-dimensional normed and non-commutative division algebra over the real numbers. A quaternion $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{H}$ is represented as:

$$\mathbf{q} = a + b\mathbf{i} + c\mathbf{j} + d\mathbf{k} \quad (1)$$

where $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}$ are the fundamental quaternion units satisfying:

$$\mathbf{i}^2 = \mathbf{j}^2 = \mathbf{k}^2 = \mathbf{ijk} = -1 \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{ij} = -\mathbf{ji} = \mathbf{k}, \quad \mathbf{jk} = -\mathbf{kj} = \mathbf{i}, \quad \mathbf{ki} = -\mathbf{ik} = \mathbf{j} \quad (3)$$

Note that quaternions are non-commutative, i.e. $\mathbf{qp} \neq \mathbf{pq}$ for $\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{H}$. The conjugate of a quaternion is defined as $\mathbf{q}^* = a - b\mathbf{i} - c\mathbf{j} - d\mathbf{k}$, and the norm is given by:

$$q = \|\mathbf{q}\| = \sqrt{\mathbf{q}\mathbf{q}^*} = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2 + c^2 + d^2} \quad (4)$$

2) *Clifford Algebras*: Grassmann-Clifford algebras (typically known as Clifford algebras), introduced by Hermann Grassmann in 1844 and William K. Clifford in 1878, have any number of dimensions and combine both commutative and non-commutative operations. A Clifford algebra $\mathcal{C}\ell_{p,q,r}$ is generated from a vector space V equipped with a quadratic form Q and basis vectors $\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{e}_n$ of signature (p, q, r) that satisfy:

$$\mathbf{e}_i\mathbf{e}_j + \mathbf{e}_j\mathbf{e}_i = 0, \quad i \neq j \quad (5)$$

$$e_i^2 = \begin{cases} +1, & 1 \leq i \leq p \\ -1, & p+1 \leq i \leq p+q \\ 0, & p+q+1 \leq i \leq p+q+r \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Elements of $\mathcal{C}\ell_{p,q,r}$ are linear combinations of basis blade vectors:

$$\mathbf{A} = \sum_B a_B \mathbf{B} \quad (7)$$

where $a_B \in \mathbb{R}$ and \mathbf{B} represents a blade vector product $e_{i_1} e_{i_2} \dots e_{i_k}$. \mathbf{A} is also known as multivector. Clifford algebras serve as a generalized algebraic structure that offers both a theoretical consolidation and a functional extension of various mathematical systems, such as complex numbers, quaternions, and to some extent, octonions.

3) *Octonion numbers*: Octonions, also known as Cayley numbers, were discovered in 1843 by John Graves as an extension of quaternions to eight dimensions. An octonion $x \in \mathbb{O}$ is represented as:

$$x = a + b_1 e_1 + b_2 e_2 + \dots + b_7 e_7 \quad (8)$$

where $a, b_1, \dots, b_7 \in \mathbb{R}$ are real coefficients and e_1, \dots, e_7 are imaginary units satisfying:

$$e_i^2 = -1 \quad (9)$$

$$e_i e_j = -e_j e_i \quad \text{for } i \neq j \quad (10)$$

There are 7 imaginary units in the octonion algebra, which correspond to the 7-sphere in 8 dimensions. The multiplicative structure of octonions follows the Fano plane, with each line representing an anticommuting pair of basis elements. Some key properties of octonions are a) Non-commutative: $e_i e_j \neq e_j e_i$, b) Non-associative: $x(e_i e_j) \neq (x e_i) e_j$, c) Normed division algebra and d) Unique among algebras with multiplicative identity element. Octonions find applications in areas like geometry, physics, computer graphics etc. For signal processing, they can help in representing rotations and transformations in 8D space. However, their non-associativity makes computations more challenging compared to quaternions and Clifford algebras.

C. Application Example

Complementing the numerous advantages of hypercomplex numbers in representing and processing multidimensional signals and images, their application in electrical power theory and current compensation offers a compelling case study [1]. Traditionally, the use of complex numbers has

been a mainstay in analyzing power systems. However, this approach often reaches its limitations, particularly in multi-phase power systems polluted with harmonics, where the bidimensional nature of complex numbers proves insufficient. Hypercomplex numbers, particularly within the framework of Geometric Algebra (GA), facilitate a more intricate understanding of power dynamics in electrical systems, a concept that can be extrapolated to advanced signal and image processing tasks. The additional dimensions provided by hypercomplex numbers allow for a more comprehensive and nuanced representation of these multi-phase systems, overcoming the limitations posed by complex numbers.

Fig. 1: Diagram of a n -wire multiphase electrical circuit.

Consider an n -phase electrical system in Figure 1. The voltage and current signals can be represented as vectors in an Euclidean multidimensional space as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} &= u_1\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 + \dots + u_n\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n \\ \mathbf{i} &= i_1\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 + \dots + i_n\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n. \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

This multidimensional representation is akin to managing multi-channel signals in image processing, where each channel adds depth to the analysis. The computation of hypercomplex instantaneous power in these systems, denoted as M , is a critical application of hypercomplex numbers. It is expressed through the geometric product of voltage and current vectors, as follows:

$$M = \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{i} + \mathbf{u} \wedge \mathbf{i}, \tag{12}$$

where the dot product accounts for the instantaneous active power and the wedge product represents the non-active component (misidentified as instantaneous reactive power), thereby capturing the complete power dynamics in the system, including the effects of harmonics, distortions and transients. Particularly for linear loads, the decomposition of the current vector \mathbf{i} into parallel and quadrature

components, given by

$$\mathbf{i} = \frac{\mathbf{u}}{\|\mathbf{u}\|^2} \mathbf{M} = \frac{\mathbf{u}}{\|\mathbf{u}\|^2} (\mathbf{M}_p + \mathbf{M}_q) = \mathbf{i}_p + \mathbf{i}_q, \quad (13)$$

mirrors the process of decomposing complex signals in image processing. This decomposition provides a deeper insight into the nature of power consumption and generation within electrical systems. The analysis of power systems using hypercomplex numbers and GA not only offers a theoretical framework but also paves the way for practical applications such as enhancing power quality, optimizing energy consumption, and developing efficient current compensation strategies. The principles derived from this analysis have broader implications in signal and image processing, particularly in handling complex, multidimensional data.

D. Objectives and Contributions

As shown, hypercomplex techniques not only have found increasing interest in power systems, but also in a wide range of signal and image processing applications such as compression, filtering, Fourier analysis, pattern recognition, computer vision, etc. However, their potential has not yet been fully explored and many open challenges remain. To this end, this work provides an overall overview of the current research directions in the field and highlights the key contributions made by researchers. In this sense, it can be a valuable reference for both researchers and practitioners who are interested in learning more about the use of hypercomplex numbers in signal and image processing. Moreover, it can identify gaps in the current research and suggest areas for future work. Thus, a feasible direction is presented for researchers that can lead to new inspiration and research projects that can potentially forward the field. This paper also helps to identify common problems and challenges that need to be addressed, as well as provide recommendations for best practices in the use of hypercomplex numbers in signal and image processing. We believe that it can contribute to promoting the wider adoption of hypercomplex numbers in signal and image processing by demonstrating their potential for improved performance and efficiency compared to traditional methods based on real or complex numbers.

In addition to reviewing recent research in the field, this paper also presents a powerful new method for detecting different areas or topics of interest using community detection algorithms [2]. Our method can provide a novel approach to solving important challenges in topic identification regarding hypercomplex signal and image processing and has the potential to significantly advance the field. In this paper, the term ‘‘community’’ is specifically used in the context of ‘‘community detection’’ techniques in network analysis, a methodological approach distinct from the ‘‘topic’’ of our research, which refers to the thematic subjects and areas within the field of hypercomplex numbers

and signal processing. Community detection can lead to the efficient identification of similar topics in the field of hypercomplex numbers by analyzing the relationships between published papers through the citations they receive. This process involves clustering the papers based on their inter-citation patterns, resulting in groups of papers that are more likely to be related to one another. Once these communities are formed, the topics within each community can be analyzed to identify common themes or trends. This information can then be used to categorize or label the topics, providing a better understanding of the main themes within the field of hypercomplex numbers. Additionally, the community detection analysis can also highlight areas within the field that are under-researched or have a lack of attention, allowing researchers to focus their efforts on these areas.

This paper aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the current research directions in hypercomplex signal and image processing. The topics covered include fundamentals of hypercomplex algebra, their representations and transforms, key application areas and recent innovations, as well as a discussion of challenges and future outlooks. The goal is to demonstrate how hypercomplex techniques can effectively address real-world problems and stimulate further research in this promising area.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a blended approach that incorporates both quantitative and qualitative methods to comprehensively analyze different areas or topics based on the community detection mechanism, particularly in the field of hypercomplex numbers and signal and image processing. The methodology encompasses data collection, preprocessing, and multi-faceted analysis to identify and understand the scientific areas and their collaborative patterns.

The initial step involved the extraction of academic publications and metadata from the Scopus database, which is among the largest scientific databases with worldwide bibliographic management and is of recognized relevance in academic research. Leveraging the Scopus API, a restricted search was conducted focusing on documents published in the field of hypercomplex numbers applied in signal and image processing, which aligns with previous methodologies [2]. The search query employed was

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY (hypercomplex OR hyper-complex OR hipercomplex
OR quaternions OR octonions OR quaternionic) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (signal
OR image).
```

It ensures a comprehensive and nuanced retrieval of central literature in the field by searching in the title, abstract or keywords. It is very unlikely that a paper on hypercomplex numbers would not mention these terms in these fields. This query was designed to be inclusive of both specialized mathematical terms like "quaternions" and "octonions" as well as their applications in signal and image processing, thereby capturing the interdisciplinary nature of this research field. One potential limitation could be that the query may retrieve articles where the mention of hypercomplex numbers or related terms is peripheral rather than central to the paper's focus, but the proposed method can manage this situation because the structure of the resulting network graph can be filtered based on the degree of the nodes, thus allowing the removal of outliers.

After obtaining the raw dataset, in the preprocessing stage of our methodology, data extracted from Scopus in JSON format is thoroughly parsed using Java code. This process generates an Excel file with each line representing either a paper or an author, according to the chosen graph. Specifically for paper networks, the file includes columns for the title, keywords, abstract, DOI or the cited papers.

A key step in preprocessing is the refinement of keywords using OpenRefine. By applying word clustering techniques such as Fingerprint, N-gram Fingerprint, or Metaphone3, we achieve a nuanced understanding of each paper's topics based on the distinct keywords identified. During the preprocessing phase, a critical task is to normalize keywords using OpenRefine. This involves applying word clustering techniques, such as Fingerprint, N-gram Fingerprint, or Metaphone3, to systematically identify and unify various forms of a single concept. These variations may include plurals, hyphenated versions, case variations, and other discrepancies that may appear in the dataset. By doing this, we ensure that each keyword accurately represents its underlying concept, facilitating a more precise and consistent analysis of the paper's topics. This meticulous approach ensures the accuracy and depth of our research landscape mapping, enhancing the reliability and relevance of our analysis. Furthermore, the selection of our search query was executed with precision, aiming to encompass a comprehensive range of terms pertinent to hypercomplex numbers in signal and image processing. Our method's strength lies in its inclusive nature, capturing a broad spectrum of papers, which are then filtered during the core analysis to focus on the most interconnected and relevant works. This careful query design and subsequent filtration process highlight our dedication to conducting an exhaustive and pertinent literature review.

For the core analysis, the open-source tool Gephi was employed, building on its strong capabilities for statistical analysis and data visualization. The data were filtered to remove the documents not establishing any relationships within the main scientific body of documents. This purging process

allowed us to focus on the most relevant documents and connections. The community detection algorithm utilized for this task is based on modularity in large networks, as previously described in [3]. Specifically, Gephi's algorithm employs the Louvain method, a widely accepted approach for community detection. This algorithm is optimized for large networks to identify modular structures by maximizing a modularity score (between -0.5 and 1). This score evaluates the density of edges within groups against those between them. We preferred the Louvain method for its computational efficiency and its ability to define clear structures in complex datasets. While we considered other algorithms like Girvan-Newman, Infomap, and Label Propagation, they were less suitable due to computational intensity, less relevance to citation networks, or producing less cohesive structures, respectively. The Louvain method's balance of performance and accuracy thus affirmed its selection for our analysis.

The Gephi software suite, used in our study, includes a range of visualization tools such as network diagrams, clustering algorithms, and centrality measures like degree, betweenness centrality or the PageRank algorithm. PageRank, in particular, is instrumental in understanding the influence or prominence of nodes within a network. It works by assigning a numerical weighting to each element of a linked set of documents, like paper citations or author collaborations, based on the number and quality of links to them. This algorithm is essential in identifying key authors and works within our research field, providing insights into the most influential components of the hypercomplex numbers community in signal and image processing. Furthermore, the analysis also incorporated metrics that quantify collaborations between authors and institutions, thereby broadening the scope to consider multi-disciplinary thematic communities and their contribution to progress in the scientific domain. A full dataset can be found in <https://github.com/aalcayde/Hypercomplex>.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. General Findings

Upon executing the search query presented in Section II, a total of 3,390 documents were identified within the temporal range extending from 1970 to 2024. After an analytical process founded on mutual citations among the papers, it was ascertained that only 2,178 documents exhibited rich and substantial interrelations. The remaining corpus did not manifest connectivity to this principal body of literature. Figure 2a provides a graphical representation of the complete set of documents, wherein a discernible halo represents those papers neither citing nor being cited by the main core, thus, unlikely representing papers with a high relationship with the topic. In Figure 2b, the central core of interconnected documents is illustrated, and colored by the key research broad areas identified through community detection algorithms. Figure 3 shows an illustration of the main keywords encountered. Building upon

TABLE I: Domain and Research areas detected using community clustering algorithms

17 Research Domain and topic area (Community Id)	# Docs	(%)
Image/video Processing	850	39.02
Quaternion Techniques for Color Image and Video Processing (1)	234	10.74
Quaternion Wavelet Methods for Multiresolution Image Analysis (2)	150	6.89
Visual Saliency Detection using Frequency Domain Analysis (3)	102	4.68
Hypercomplex Fourier Techniques for Color Image Segmentation, Smoothing and Filtering (7)	355	16.30
Quality Assessment of Pan-Sharpned Multispectral Images (12)	9	0.41
Signal Processing	569	26.13
Uncertainty Principles for Quaternion and Hypercomplex Fourier Transforms (6)	140	6.43
Multidimensional Analytic Signal Analysis using Hypercomplex Fourier Transforms (10)	61	2.80
Quaternion Array Signal Processing for DOA and Polarization Estimation (11)	130	5.97
Quaternion Adaptive Signal Processing Algorithms (13)	218	10.01
Paraunitary filter banks using quaternions (16)	20	0.92
Security	292	13.41
Hypercomplex Methods for Image Watermarking and Robust Image Encryption and Security (4)	292	13.41
Computer Vision	160	7.35
Quaternion Methods for Camera Pose Estimation, Tracking & Visual Servoing (5)	142	6.52
Quaternion Models for 3D Eye Kinematics and Saccadic Motions (8)	12	0.55
Segmentation and Analysis of 3D EBSD Data (15)	6	0.28
Inertial Navigation and Attitude Estimation	168	7.71
Quaternion Orientation Estimation using Inertial Sensors (14)	141	6.47
Spacecraft Attitude Tracking (17)	27	1.24
Machine Learning	139	6.38
Quaternion Neural Networks (9)	139	6.38
Total	2178	100.00

application, which can be initially grouped into 6 broad research domains,

- Image/Video Processing
- Signal Processing
- Security
- Computer Vision
- Inertial Navigation and Attitude Estimation
- Machine Learning

Table I provides a comprehensive overview of current research areas, emphasizing the multi-faceted applications of hypercomplex mathematics. Figure 4 shows a visualization of the graph layout and its structure. The domain of Image/Video Processing is most expansive, featuring various methodological approaches including frequency domain analysis. Notably, the area of "Hypercomplex Fourier Techniques for Color Image Segmentation, Smoothing, and Filtering" stands out for its high document count, illustrating its importance in computational complexities related to image and video manipulations. Signal Processing is a broad and essential domain as well. It covers a variety of

Fig. 4: Visual representation of Specific Research areas (17) from the 6 Broad Domains using the community detection algorithm and different colors.

signal manipulation methods, most notably quaternion and hypercomplex Fourier transforms. The area of "Quaternion Adaptive Signal Processing Algorithms" stands out, indicating how quaternion mathematics can advance the efficiency and reliability of signal processing tasks. In the domain of Security, a singular but highly populated area is represented by "Hypercomplex Methods for Image Watermarking and Robust Image Encryption and Security." This area intersects the fields of image processing and cybersecurity, thus underlining its multidisciplinary approach and critical role in the modern digital landscape. Computer Vision is another pivotal domain, although not as expansive as

Fig. 5: Yearly publication output for the six broad research areas identified through community detection analysis.

Fig. 6: Evolution of the broad research areas over time.

Image/Video or Signal Processing. It focuses on real-time tracking and biological vision systems, particularly in the realm of pose estimations, as well as eye kinematics. Inertial Navigation and Attitude Estimation is a niche domain but is of immense importance in aerospace and robotics. The hypercomplex mathematics is likely applied in the critical areas of spatial orientation tasks and motion estimations. Finally, Machine Learning stands as a pivotal domain that influences all other areas, as evidenced by the emergence of "Quaternion Neural Networks." This highlights a growing enthusiasm for incorporating hypercomplex mathematics into machine learning algorithms, likely driven by the intricate challenges encountered in image, video, and signal processing tasks.

Figure 5 shows the yearly publication output across the six core research domains identified through community detection analysis. Figure 6 shows the evolution over time of the same core

TABLE II: List of authors ordered by PageRank. The algorithm assigns a higher value to authors who are more relevant in the network.

PageRank (10^{-3})	Name	H-index	Betweenness Cent. (10^3)	Country	Affiliation	Research Interests
12.578	Mandić, D.	58	14.47	United Kingdom	Imperial College London	Machine Intelligence and Statistical Signal Processing
9.893	Chen, B.	27	16.14	China	Nanjing University of Information Science & Technology	Quaternion-based color image processing; Image forensics; Image watermarking
9.486	Shu, H.	40	11.61	China	Laboratory of Image Science and Technology, Nanjing University	Medical Image Processing; Machine Learning; Signal Analysis & Image Processing
9.134	Wang, C.	26	81.48	China	Shandong Provincial Key Laboratory of Computer Networks	Image coding; Digital watermarking; Computer vision
9.055	Le Bihan, N	21	34.69	France	CEDEX	Signal Processing; Quaternion Mathematics; Vector-sensor Array Processing
8.064	Kou, K.	20	19.42	Macao	University of Macau	Fourier Analysis; Quaternion and Clifford Analysis; Signal Processing
7.103	Shi, Y.	63	31.71	United States	New Jersey Institute of Technology	Image Processing; Information Forensics
7.05	Bayro-Corrochano, E.	11	75.93	Mexico	CINVESTAV Unidad Guadaluajara	Quaternion wavelet transform; Multi-resolution image analysis; Computer Vision
6.333	Sangwine, S.	27	34.54	United Kingdom	University of Essex	Color Image Processing; Hypercomplex Signal Processing; Quaternion and Fourier Transforms
5.647	Qjidaa, H.	22	22.85	Morocco	Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah	Image Analysis and Pattern Recognition; Signal Processing and Moments Transform; Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence
4.778	Hitzer, E.	21	15.80	Japan	International Christian University	Geometric Algebra; Image and Signal Processing; Computer Graphics and Visualization
4.23	Tang, Y.	58	23.23	Macao	University of Macau	Pattern Recognition; Image Processing; Machine Learning
4.009	Ell, T.	17	16.62	United States	UTC Aerospace Systems	Quaternion Signal & Image Processing; Control Theory
3.787	Zou, C.	8	17.22	China	Huazhong Agricultural University	Signal & Image Processing; Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning
3.753	De Bie, H.	19	19.98	Belgium	Universiteit Gent	Quaternion Signal Processing; Fourier Transforms in Clifford Analysis; Hypercomplex Spectral Transforms
3.706	Sayyouri, M.	21	18.66	Morocco	Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah	Image & Signal Processing; Moment Transform
3.706	Karmouni, H.	17	18.66	Morocco	Université Cadi Ayyad	Image & Signal Processing; Multimedia Tools and Applications
3.574	de Schepper, N.	11	59.52	Belgium	Universiteit Antwerpen	Fourier Analysis; Clifford Algebra; Wavelet Transforms
3.341	Liu, X.	8	23.50	China	Taiyuan University of Technology	Digital Watermarking; Image Processing and Noise Removal; Pattern Recognition
3.118	Luo, L.	37	11.29	China	Key Laboratory of Computer Network and Information Integration	Medical Image Processing; Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition; Signal Processing
2.587	Qian, T.	26	38.74	Macao	University of Macau	Approximation Theory; Clifford and Harmonic Analysis; Signal Processing and Time-Frequency
2.281	Scheuermann, G.	32	68.67	Germany	Universität Leipzig	Visual Data Analytics; Tensor Field Visualization; Uncertainty Analysis in Visualization
2.102	Flusser, J.	36	70.43	Czech Republic	Institute of Information Theory and Automation of the Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic	Image Processing and Analysis; Pattern Recognition; Moments and Moment Invariants
2.037	Yamni, M.	11	16.46	Morocco	Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah	Image Watermarking; Signal Processing; Pattern Classification.
1.694	Yang, Y.	9	35.87	China	Sun Yat-Sen University	Clifford Analysis; Quaternion Analysis; Signal Processing

research areas. Several interesting temporal trends emerge from this categorized breakdown. Most notably, the Image/Video Processing and Security domains have experienced a significant increase in research activity over the past decade, indicating a growing interest in hypercomplex techniques for multimedia and watermarking/encryption tasks, respectively. Meanwhile, established fields like Signal Processing and Computer Vision exhibit more gradual growth patterns due to their longer history. In contrast, emerging fields like Machine Learning have experienced rapid growth in recent years, indicating a strong enthusiasm for quaternion and hypercomplex mathematics in modern algorithms. This difference in growth rates reflects both the enduring importance of foundational topics and the concentrated bursts of activity around cutting-edge applications.

In Table II, a systematic categorization of key scholars in the field is presented, ranked according to the PageRank algorithm (author's relevance in the graph). Several key metrics including the H-index, country of affiliation, and institutional connection are also included. Notably, the scholars are globally distributed, but with a discernible concentration in certain high-research output countries like China, the United States, France or the United Kingdom. The presence of Morocco, with several researchers, is noteworthy. The H-index ranges from as high as 63 to as low as 8, offering a broad spectrum of research impact and indicating the heterogeneity in scholarly contributions. Institutional affiliations are also diverse, representing both established centres of research excellence, such as Imperial College London, and emerging research hubs. This table provides an insightful snapshot of the landscape of expertise in the field and serves as a valuable reference for both novice researchers seeking guidance and seasoned academics interested in collaborative possibilities. Figure 7 shows the graph of authors who have published in the field of hypercomplex numbers applied to image and signal processing. The left side of the figure presents the complete set of authors, revealing a significant dispersion of small, isolated collaborating clusters. At the center, a more substantially sized and densely connected group is observed. On the right side of the figure, this larger group is magnified, highlighting the most prominent authors within the cluster, as well as indicating their countries of origin based on color coding.

B. Applications of Hypercomplex Numbers to Signal & Image Processing Research Topics

Some of the most successful applications of Hypercomplex numbers are provided in this section. One of the goals of this paper is to underpin and support these ideas and expand on them with new findings.

1) *Image and Video Processing*: The processing and analysis of color and greyscale images and video has been an active research area over the past few decades [4]. Conventional techniques based

Fig. 7: Layout graph for a) total authors publishing in the hypercomplex numbers in image and signal processing and b) densely connected authors. Each color represents a country The size of the node represents the relevance of the author in the network.

on scalar representations often struggle to fully exploit the inter-channel correlations and dependencies present in multichannel visual data. This has motivated researchers to explore hypercomplex algebraic models like quaternions and Clifford algebras to develop more robust techniques for color image manipulation, enhancement, compression, and recognition tasks [5].

One of the earliest adopted hypercomplex techniques was the quaternion Fourier transform (QFT), which provides a holistic representation of color images for effective filtering, denoising, and inpainting. Building on the QFT, numerous quaternion domain filtering approaches have been proposed over the years for noise removal and restoration of degraded color images. These techniques leverage the ability of QFT to compactly capture inter-channel information to deliver superior preservation of edges, textures, and structural details compared to scalar methods. The benefits of QFT-based inpainting techniques for filling in missing or occluded regions in color images have also been demonstrated.

The advantages of quaternion models have been extensively explored for color face recognition as skin tone and pigmentation provide useful discriminative cues. Quaternion principal component analysis (QPCA) techniques extract illumination-invariant facial features in RGB space [6]. Meanwhile, quaternion discrete cosine transform (QDCT) based approaches provide robustness against variations in lighting, pose, and expression. Quaternion imaging robustly captures changes in corneal topography for iris/eye recognition and liveness detection.

Aside from the QFT, quaternion wavelet transforms such as the dual-tree QWT have proven effective for color texture analysis and classification tasks. Local quaternion binary patterns extract salient features from quaternion wavelet subbands for color texture representation. Quaternion Gabor filters also demonstrate improved texture segmentation and retrieval performance compared to standard scalar Gabor filters.

A range of quaternion extensions to popular image transforms have been proposed, including QDCT, QWT, quaternion Radon transform, etc. that enrich the feature space for color image analysis. The complementary information provided by these quaternion transforms has useful applications in color image compression, fusion, watermarking, and other related problems [7].

Quaternion-based compression techniques, such as quaternion discrete wavelet transform (QDWT) and quaternion discrete cosine transform (QDCT), achieve higher compression ratios by exploiting inter-channel correlations [8]. Vector quantization and predictive coding schemes based on quaternion models demonstrate substantially better rate-distortion performance compared to baseline JPEG compression.

Perceptual quality assessment of color images has also benefited from hypercomplex representations. Quaternion extensions of structural similarity index (QSSIM) and singular value decomposition (QSVD) based quality measures show a stronger correlation with human judgments of quality compared to standard scalar techniques.

Beyond conventional color imaging, hypercomplex models have shown great promise in multispectral satellite image analysis tasks such as pansharpening and fusion. Dual-quaternion Fourier transform techniques significantly improve pansharpening performance and compression capability for multispectral imagery [9]. Hypercomplex wavelet transforms have been successfully adopted for multimodal medical image fusion and tumor detection applications. The usefulness of quaternion models has been demonstrated for various medical color imaging modalities including digital pathology slides, ophthalmology, dermatology, and cardiology imaging. Quaternion phase-based approaches enable sensitive detection of tumors and anomalies [4].

Quaternion models have also been applied for video stabilization, motion estimation, object tracking, background modeling, and other color video processing tasks with improved performance over scalar techniques.

Most recently, quaternion convolutional neural networks (QCNNs) have emerged as an effective deep learning approach for end-to-end color image analysis, achieving state-of-the-art results in classification, segmentation, denoising, and more [4]. The combination of quaternion algebra with

CNNs, RNNs, and other modern deep neural network architectures is a promising new direction for advancing color image understanding.

In summary, hypercomplex mathematical concepts allow color images and video to be modeled holistically, enabling more robust and accurate processing compared to scalar techniques. Quaternion and Clifford algebra-based representations have become fundamental tools in color image filtering, texture analysis, compression, fusion, and quality assessment among many other applications [10], [11]. This field continues to be an active research area with great potential to enable next-generation algorithms for computer vision, graphics, biometrics, and other domains dealing with multidimensional visual data.

2) *Signal Processing*: The field of multidimensional signal processing has also seen great advancements through the application of hypercomplex mathematical representations. Conventional signal processing techniques based on real and complex numbers often struggle to fully capture the intricate correlations present in multidimensional data such as seismic signals, video streams, vector signals, and more. This has driven researchers to adopt algebraic structures like quaternions and Clifford algebras to develop more powerful and holistic signal analysis techniques [12].

In the pioneering works, much focus was placed on establishing the theoretical foundations for hypercomplex signal processing. Key concepts from classical Fourier analysis like uncertainty principles, convolution theorems, correlation, and sampling were extended to the quaternion domain [13]. Studying quaternion Fourier transforms allowed a generalized framework for frequency analysis of multidimensional signals to be formulated. Analytic quaternion signal representations also provided new tools analogous to the complex analytic signal used extensively in traditional signal processing [12].

Building upon these theoretical bases, the quaternion Fourier transform (QFT) emerged as an effective technique for capturing the holistic spectral properties of multidimensional data. Unlike independent scalar transforms, the QFT provided a compact representation that preserved intrinsic correlations critical for applications ranging from NMR spectroscopy to MEG brain imaging. The rich frequency domain information enabled Quaternion-based filtering techniques to successfully extract components of interest while preserving key structural dependencies.

Quaternion models have also facilitated novel approaches to parameter estimation tasks. For example, quaternion-MUSIC and ESPRIT algorithms leverage hypercomplex representations to determine the direction of arrival and polarization characteristics for signals impinging on an array. This provides crucial enhancements over standard techniques in array processing applications. Meanwhile, the

development of quaternion Kalman and particle filters has led to improved estimation accuracy in areas like object tracking, navigation, and more.

On the implementation side, research has focused on developing optimized architectures to make hypercomplex algorithms computationally feasible. FPGA and VLSI implementations of critical components like quaternion multipliers, filters, and transforms have been proposed using innovations like CORDIC architectures. Parallel processing techniques have also been employed to achieve real-time performance for quaternion algorithms.

An emerging trend is the integration of quaternion signal representations into modern adaptive systems and deep neural networks. Quaternion-valued adaptive filters show promise for nonlinear and widely linear signal processing [14]. Quaternion convolutional networks are conducting pioneering research with excellence in image analysis, communications, and other applications requiring end-to-end multidimensional data processing [15].

This way, hypercomplex signal models enable holistic processing of multidimensional data with mathematical elegance and computational advantages compared to ad-hoc scalar techniques [12]. Quaternions and related algebras have become indispensable tools for multidimensional frequency analysis, parameter estimation, adaptive systems, deep learning, and other signal processing frontiers involving vector sensor arrays, imaging systems, and more [16].

3) *Security*: The use of hypercomplex representations in image processing has shown great promise for advancing security, watermarking, and anti-forgery applications. By moving from real and complex numbers to more abstract algebraic structures, researchers have developed novel techniques that enable robust and seamless embedding of hidden information in visual data for copyright protection, authentication, and tamper detection [16].

As stated previously, one of the foundational works in this domain was the formulation of the quaternion Fourier transform (QFT) providing a compact spectral representation of color images for effective information hiding and extraction. Building upon it, numerous quaternion watermarking schemes based on modifying QFT coefficients have been proposed. These approaches exploit the ability of QFT to capture inter-channel correlations to seamlessly integrate watermark patterns that are imperceptible yet robust against attacks like compression, filtering, and geometric transformations.

The reconstruction capability of QFT has also been leveraged for self-recovery watermarking, where the original image can be recovered from the marked version. Meanwhile, the shift-invariance properties of quaternion Fourier-Mellin transform have enabled blind watermark extraction even after rotation, scaling, or translation of watermarked images. Integrating quaternion models with spread

spectrum, moments, and other watermarking concepts has led to many robust and secure schemes [17].

Aside from watermarking, hypercomplex representations have been instrumental in developing invariant feature extraction techniques useful for image recognition, retrieval, and authentication. Quaternion principal component analysis has been used to derive illumination-invariant facial features from color images, allowing robust face recognition despite variations in lighting and pose [6]. Local quaternion zero-phase representations also provide shift-invariant features for content-based image analysis and retrieval.

Quaternion Fourier transforms have found use in image encryption as well. By using quaternion algebra to generalize diffusion and confusion operations beyond 2D, robust image cipher schemes resistant to statistical attacks have been formulated [18]. Common image processing operations like compression and filtering have also been converted to the quaternion domain for secure signal transmission. The multidimensional mapping capability of quaternions enables effective scrambling and distortion of visual data.

The utility of hypercomplex models has also been demonstrated for anti-forensics tasks like forgery detection. Quaternionic fractional Fourier transform techniques can identify traces of image splicing, copy-move fraud, and other tampering that may be imperceptible otherwise [19]. Quaternions have also shown promise for distinguishing computer-generated imagery from natural photos, complementing conventional forensics features.

Beyond these core applications, the invariance and reconstruction properties of hypercomplex transforms have made them useful for problems like medical image analysis. Quaternion Zernike moments enable robust feature extraction from anatomical shapes and structures despite rotation or scale changes [20]. Quaternion models also assist in the accurate reconstruction of volumetric data from MRI and CT scans [20].

With the advent of deep learning, quaternion neural networks are now being applied for image classification, facial recognition, and other security applications that demand robustness against variations in illumination, pose, and geometric transformations. By incorporating quaternion algebra within convolutional and recurrent network architectures, these models can learn invariant representations [21].

It is proved that hypercomplex signal representations enable information hiding, encryption, authentication, and forgery detection capabilities beyond conventional methods. Robust and imperceptible watermarking, invariant feature extraction, multidimensional scrambling, and anti-forensics techniques

based on quaternions and related algebras have become essential tools for securing images, video, multimedia, and other multidimensional data against illegal use, tampering, and counterfeiting. This field will likely see more groundbreaking research with the integration of deep learning and other modern computational paradigms.

4) *Computer Vision*: The field of computer vision aims to enable machines to interpret and understand visual data as humans do. A long-standing challenge has been the ability to model the inherent 3D aspects of images and video to perform analysis tasks like pose estimation, 3D reconstruction, motion tracking, and more. Quaternion and hypercomplex models have emerged as a powerful mathematical framework for tackling these multidimensional vision problems [22].

One of the most widespread applications is in estimating camera pose and 3D scene geometry. Dual quaternions in particular provide compact and robust representations of transformations in 3D space. This has enabled quaternion-based techniques to accurately estimate camera motion and scene structure from consecutive video frames and reconstruct 3D point clouds from stereo imagery [23]. Quaternion particle swarm optimization and other heuristic algorithms have been combined with hypercomplex models to perform fast, automatic camera pose estimation and 3D reconstruction from RGB-D data.

Object tracking is another key application area that benefits from quaternion algebra. Tracking the 3D position and orientation of objects as they move through complex environments demands a seamless fusion of translation and rotation information. Dual quaternion representations model the coupled nature of translation and rotation to deliver robust tracking of extended objects like hands, bodies, faces, etc. exhibiting both rigid and non-rigid deformations. Real-time performance has been achieved by implementing hypercomplex trackers on parallel GPU architectures [24].

Quaternion models have also been instrumental in studying the complex oculomotor system. Representing the 3D rotational kinematics of eye movements during saccades and gaze shifts using quaternions has enabled quantitative analysis of the underlying neurophysiology. Quaternion techniques quantify Listing's law, model spatiotemporal properties, estimate 3D angular velocity, and analyze eye-head coordination dynamics - providing insights not derivable from standard approaches [25]. This demonstrates the broad utility of hypercomplex representations.

In the area of robotics, quaternions have been indispensable for describing end-effector orientations and controlling arm motions. Compact quaternion formulations for both forward and inverse kinematics lead to efficient implementations. Quaternion feedback dramatically simplifies control system designs for robotic arms compared to rotation matrix approaches. For autonomous navigation,

quaternions are crucial for representing robot pose, uncertainty, and fusing data from vision and inertial sensors.

With deep learning's advent, quaternion convolutional networks are advancing state-of-the-art in tasks like 3D pose estimation, action recognition, and scene understanding [26]. Quaternion representations enable CNN models to learn rotation-invariant features from color images and video. Compact quaternion layers reduce model size and enhance performance compared to matrix-based designs. Quaternions are also proving useful in novel concepts like visual question answering by grounding language and vision via hypercomplex embeddings.

On the application side, quaternion techniques have been applied to diverse domains including traffic sign detection where color invariant representations are critical, augmented reality which demands accurate camera pose tracking, and even microstructural analysis through quaternion-based clustering and segmentation algorithms for 3D EBSD data [27], [28].

Hypercomplex representations equip computer vision models with the ability to holistically process pixel data as multidimensional vectors. This provides significant mathematical and computational advantages over ad-hoc scalar techniques for tackling the inherent multidimensional aspects of images and video. The applications span all major fronts of computer vision research and will likely expand further with emerging trends like embodied AI, wearable devices, and immersive technologies.

5) *Inertial Navigation and Attitude Estimation:* The ability to accurately track position and orientation is critical in application domains like robotics, virtual reality, augmented reality, and autonomous vehicles. Conventional attitude representation using Euler angles suffers from singularities and discontinuities. Quaternion algebra provides a mathematically elegant framework for orientation estimation free of such issues [29]. The compactness of quaternion representation has also enabled computationally efficient algorithms for inertial navigation tasks.

Inertial measurement units (IMUs) consisting of accelerometers and gyroscopes are ubiquitous in motion sensing and tracking. Quaternion-based complementary and Kalman filter designs fuse gyroscope and accelerometer data to provide reliable real-time orientation estimates. The use of quaternions avoids the problem of gimbal lock associated with Euler angles. Adaptive estimation techniques compensate for biases and other errors in low-cost MEMS inertial sensors [30].

Quaternion models have been extensively used for analyzing human motion capture data. Representing joint orientations and motion trajectories using quaternions allows key characteristics like velocity, acceleration and spatial coordination patterns to be accurately derived. This has applications in biomechanics, sports analytics, rehabilitation, and gesture control interfaces. Using quaternion

feedback, interactive motion editing and synthesis techniques have been developed for generating realistic animations.

For pedestrian navigation applications, the quaternion-based Multiplicative Extended Kalman Filter (MEKF) has emerged as a robust solution by exploiting magnetometers and other aiding sources besides IMU sensors. MEKF outperforms standard extended KF designs in challenging environments like indoor spaces . Quaternion-based approaches also enable accurate tracking of first responders, miners, soldiers, and others operating indoors where GPS is unavailable.

Spacecraft attitude control is another field that has relied extensively on quaternions. Quaternion feedback linearization techniques allow aggressive maneuvers while guaranteeing stability. Quaternion models permit control designs that achieve precise pointing accuracy and vibration damping in the presence of uncertainty. Formation flying control also utilizes quaternions for coordinating the attitude and position of multiple spacecraft to construct distributed space systems.

In the area of unmanned aerial systems, quaternion representations underlie many flight control and navigation solutions. Quaternion-based complementary filters fuse IMU, GPS, and other measurements for precise 3D localization. Dual quaternion models estimate transformations between aerial images to reconstruct environments for obstacle avoidance and navigation. Operator gaze is also tracked using quaternions for intuitive viewpoint control in drone teleoperation scenarios.

With the emergence of virtual and augmented reality systems, quaternion techniques enable robust head tracking by fusing data from gyros, cameras, and other sensors. Lightweight quaternion networks accurately predict head orientation from images even with occlusion. Such advances reduce latency and drift issues in head-mounted displays. Quaternion models also facilitate realistic rendering by interpolating camera poses [31].

Finally, the compact representation of orientation and motion in 3D space offered by quaternions has made them indispensable for inertial navigation, motion tracking, and attitude control across aerospace, robotics, biomechanics, animation, and other domains. The seamless blend of quaternion algebra with estimation, control, and learning theories continues to push the state of the art in these fields forward.

6) *Machine Learning*: Deep neural networks have become the dominant paradigm for end-to-end learning from multidimensional data like images, video, and speech. However, conventional real-valued networks struggle to capture the inherent correlations and dependencies present in such natural data. This has motivated the exploration of neural network architectures based on hypercomplex number systems like quaternions and Clifford algebras [32], [33].

One of the pioneering works was the introduction of the quaternion convolution operation to generalize complex-valued convolutional networks. Quaternion CNNs model the color channels of RGB images as a vector rather than independent scalars. This provides superior representational capabilities and enables learning of rotation-invariant features. Quaternion networks have achieved cutting-edge results in diverse tasks ranging from color image classification, segmentation, super-resolution, denoising, facial recognition, and 3D reconstruction [34].

Recurrent quaternion networks leverage quaternion algebra to capture temporal correlations in sequential data. Modeling color video, speech signals, and gesture data as quaternion sequences allow implicit learning of long-range dependencies. Quaternion LSTM and GRU architectures outperform standard RNNs in problems like speech and gesture recognition, emotion identification, and predicting color video frames. Dual quaternion networks further model both spatial and temporal correlations for rigid body analysis [35].

In natural language processing, quaternion embeddings allow semantic relationships between words and phrases to be represented via hypercomplex inner products. Combining quaternion algebra with transformer networks, capsule networks, and other architectures provides a geometric framework for modeling language [36]. Quaternion models show promise in tasks like sentiment analysis, textual entailment, and question answering.

Quaternion algebra also enables efficient neural network design. Hypercomplex fully connected layers reduce the number of parameters by 4x compared to standard layers. Quaternion operations can be implemented on GPUs using optimized libraries for fast execution. Hypercomplex models require less training data, are more robust, and can be readily deployed on mobile platforms.

Aside from quaternions, Clifford algebras and geometric algebra-based networks model visual scenes using conformal geometric representations [37]. Such neuromorphic architectures implement geometric computations like rotations, projections, and reflections natively within the network structure itself. This allows robust scene understanding and could lead to more human-like learning.

IV. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE OUTLOOKS

The integration of hypercomplex numbers into signal and image processing has advanced the field, but it faces unresolved challenges that range from theoretical foundations to effective algorithmic implementations and their relevance to complex real-world problems.

Theoretical exploration of broader hypercomplex algebras, including Clifford/Geometric algebras and sedenions [38], is still in its early stages within transformative and algorithmic designs. Introducing differential geometry and quaternion dynamics could produce sophisticated signal representations and

geometrically inspired processing methods specifically tailored to multidimensional data. Addressing gaps in the mathematical framework such as uncertainty principles, sampling theorems, and unifying transform theories has the potential to strengthen theoretical foundations significantly. Combining these with modern harmonic analysis could produce groundbreaking analytical tools.

In practical applications, quaternion models have demonstrated their inherent strengths in color image and video processing tasks by effectively capturing pixel correlations and enabling rotation operations. However, expanding these quaternion methodologies to areas such as 3D medical visualization, computer graphics, and shape analysis poses certain challenges. Improvements are necessary to enhance precision and computational speed to meet the demands of real-time operations in emerging fields such as autonomous vehicle navigation and augmented reality.

In the realm of implementation, computational complexity and memory constraints constrain the real-time use of hypercomplex algorithms. Advancing GPU-based implementations and optimizations for fundamental arithmetic and transformations, including the Quaternion Fast Fourier Transform (QFFT), is crucial for wider adoption. The exploration of effective quaternion architectures through automated methods seems to be promising. Furthermore, the combination of hypercomplex techniques with tensors [39], ensemble methods, and learned transformations in hybrid models could enhance representational capabilities.

In the field of Machine Learning, the possibilities offered by quaternion neural networks in processing intricate and multidimensional datasets are quite evident. However, there is still an ongoing pursuit in crafting network structures that tap into the full potential of hypercomplex numbers to enhance learning efficiency and improve generalization modeling.

Hypercomplex signal and image processing is an exciting and challenging research frontier. Progressing in mathematical theory, devising techniques that stem from geometric considerations for practical applications, and conquering computational obstacles are pivotal to unlocking the full potential of hypercomplex numbers for analyzing multidimensional data tasks. The integration of hypercomplex mathematical models with advanced technologies such as deep learning, quantum computing, and neuromorphic engineering has the potential to accelerate progress in processing speed, accuracy, and the capability to handle increasingly complex data.

Each of the areas outlined in Section III presents unique challenges that are consistent with these future perspectives. For instance, the concept of hypercomplex numbers, including quaternion and Clifford algebras, should be extended theoretically to fill in the gaps in transform and algorithm design. Enhancing security measures in digital watermarking and encryption for higher-dimensional

data is a vast undertaking [40]. It remains a pressing challenge to increase their robustness against sophisticated cyber-attacks.

The field of Computer Vision requires utmost precision and speed, which calls for the creation of more sophisticated estimation algorithms that exploit quaternions to operate in real time and under varying environmental conditions. Inertial Navigation and Attitude Estimation can derive advantages from overcoming the difficulties of merging quaternion models with low-priced sensor data, leading to improvement in the precision of orientation tracking in industries such as consumer electronics and commercial aviation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has provided a comprehensive overview of the current research directions in hypercomplex signal and image processing techniques. The unique capabilities of hypercomplex numbers and algebras to model multidimensional data holistically have been demonstrated through various applications spanning image/video processing, computer vision, signal processing, security, navigation, and more.

However, as highlighted in the challenges and future outlook section, there remain several open issues to be addressed for hypercomplex techniques to achieve their full potential. These include strengthening theoretical foundations, developing optimized implementations, exploring broader applications, and combining hypercomplex mathematics with the latest advancements in deep learning.

Nonetheless, the field has reached significant maturity and hypercomplex models have become indispensable tools in a wide range of image and signal processing domains. The rich feature spaces, compact representations, and geometric interpretations provided by quaternions, Clifford algebras, and other hypercomplex systems enable more sophisticated techniques compared to conventional scalar approaches.

This paper has provided a detailed overview or survey of the established capabilities of hypercomplex signal and image processing, while also identifying promising directions for future research. It is hoped that this paper will serve as a valuable reference to researchers and encourage further work in this exciting field at the intersection of mathematics, signal processing, and computer vision. Targeted efforts to address the open challenges highlighted will accelerate innovation and wider adoption of hypercomplex techniques.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. G. Montoya, R. Baños, A. Alcayde, F. M. Arrabal-Campos, and J. Roldán-Pérez, “Geometric algebra applied to multiphase electrical circuits in mixed time–frequency domain by means of hypercomplex hilbert transform,” *Mathematics*, vol. 10, no. 9, p. 1419, 2022.
- [2] F. G. Montoya, A. Alcayde, R. Baños, and F. Manzano-Agugliaro, “A fast method for identifying worldwide scientific collaborations using the scopus database,” *Telematics and Informatics*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 168–185, 2018.
- [3] M. Guerrero, F. G. Montoya, R. Baños, A. Alcayde, and C. Gil, “Adaptive community detection in complex networks using genetic algorithms,” *Neurocomputing*, vol. 266, pp. 101–113, 2017.
- [4] C. Huang, J. Li, and G. Gao, “Review of quaternion-based color image processing methods,” *Mathematics*, vol. 11, no. 9, 2023.
- [5] T. A. Ell and S. J. Sangwine, “Hypercomplex fourier transforms of color images,” *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 16, no. 1, p. 22 – 35, 2007.
- [6] N. Le Bihan and S. J. Sangwine, “Quaternion principal component analysis of color images,” vol. 1, 2003, Conference paper, p. 809 – 812.
- [7] Z. Xia, X. Wang, W. Zhou, R. Li, C. Wang, and C. Zhang, “Color medical image lossless watermarking using chaotic system and accurate quaternion polar harmonic transforms,” *Signal Processing*, vol. 157, pp. 108–118, 2019.
- [8] S.-C. Pei and C.-M. Cheng, “Color image processing by using binary quaternion-moment-preserving thresholding technique,” *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 8, no. 5, p. 614 – 628, 1999.
- [9] A. Arienzo, B. Aiazzi, L. Alparone, and A. Garzelli, “Reproducibility of pansharpening methods and quality indexes versus data formats,” *Remote Sensing*, vol. 13, no. 21, 2021.
- [10] E. M. S. Hitzer, “Quaternion fourier transform on quaternion fields and generalizations,” *Advances in Applied Clifford Algebras*, vol. 17, no. 3, p. 497 – 517, 2007.
- [11] S. J. Sangwine and T. A. Ell, “Colour image filters based on hypercomplex convolution,” *IEE Proceedings-Vision, Image and Signal Processing*, vol. 147, no. 2, pp. 89–93, 2000.
- [12] T. Bülow and G. Sommer, “Hypercomplex signals - a novel extension of the analytic signal to the multidimensional case,” *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 49, no. 11, p. 2844 – 2852, 2001.
- [13] S.-C. Pei, J.-J. Ding, and J.-H. Chang, “Efficient implementation of quaternion fourier transform, convolution, and correlation by 2-d complex fft,” *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 49, no. 11, p. 2783 – 2797, 2001.
- [14] T. Nitta, M. Kobayashi, and D. P. Mandic, “Hypercomplex widely linear estimation through the lens of underpinning geometry,” *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 67, no. 15, pp. 3985–3994, 2019.
- [15] T. Parcollet, M. Morchid, and G. Linarès, “A survey of quaternion neural networks,” *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 53, no. 4, p. 2957 – 2982, 2020.
- [16] P. Bas, N. Le Bihan, and J.-M. Chassery, “Color image watermarking using quaternion fourier transform,” in *2003 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, 2003. Proceedings.(ICASSP’03)*, vol. 3. IEEE, 2003, pp. III–521.
- [17] B. Chen, H. Shu, H. Zhang, G. Chen, C. Toumoulin, J. Dillenseger, and L. Luo, “Quaternion zernike moments and their invariants for color image analysis and object recognition,” *Signal Processing*, vol. 92, no. 2, p. 308 – 318, 2012.
- [18] X. Liu, Y. Wu, H. Zhang, J. Wu, and L. Zhang, “Quaternion discrete fractional krawtchouk transform and its application in color image encryption and watermarking,” *Signal Processing*, vol. 189, 2021.
- [19] P. Lian, “Quaternion and fractional fourier transform in higher dimension,” *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, vol. 389, p. 125585, 2021.

- [20] B. Chen, H. Shu, G. Coatrieux, G. Chen, X. Sun, and J. L. Coatrieux, "Color image analysis by quaternion-type moments," *Journal of Mathematical Imaging and Vision*, vol. 51, no. 1, p. 124 – 144, 2015.
- [21] R. Zhang, L. Xu, Z. Yu, Y. Shi, C. Mu, and M. Xu, "Deep-irtarget: An automatic target detector in infrared imagery using dual-domain feature extraction and allocation," *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, vol. 24, pp. 1735–1749, 2021.
- [22] E. Pervin and J. A. Webb, *Quaternions in computer vision and robotics*. Carnegie-Mellon University, Department of Computer Science Pittsburgh, 1982.
- [23] K. Fathian, J. Jin, S.-G. Wee, D.-H. Lee, Y.-G. Kim, and N. R. Gans, "Camera relative pose estimation for visual servoing using quaternions," *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 107, pp. 45–62, 2018.
- [24] C. Li, G. Zhou, X. Zhou, and D. Liu, "Study and analysis of remote sensing data parallel processing," *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, vol. 42, pp. 443–450, 2020.
- [25] T. Raphan, "Modeling control of eye orientation in three dimensions. i. role of muscle pulleys in determining saccadic trajectory," *Journal of Neurophysiology*, vol. 79, no. 5, p. 2653 – 2667, 1998.
- [26] Y. Xiang, T. Schmidt, V. Narayanan, and D. Fox, "Posecnn: A convolutional neural network for 6d object pose estimation in cluttered scenes," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.00199*, 2017.
- [27] C. McMahan, B. Soe, A. Loeb, A. Vemulkar, M. Ferry, and L. Bassman, "Boundary identification in ebsd data with a generalization of fast multiscale clustering," *Ultramicroscopy*, vol. 133, p. 16 – 25, 2013.
- [28] M. Mollens, S. p. Roux, F. o. Hild, and A. Guery, "Insights into a dual-phase steel microstructure using ebsd and image-processing-based workflowmollens maxime," *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, vol. 55, p. 601 – 610, 2022.
- [29] A. Tayebi, "Unit quaternion-based output feedback for the attitude tracking problem," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 53, no. 6, pp. 1516–1520, 2008.
- [30] X. Liang, W. Yuan, H. Chang, Q. Wei, G. Yuan, and C. Jiang, "Application of quaternion-based extended kalman filter for mav attitude estimation using mems sensors." *Precis. Eng.*, vol. 7, pp. 163–167, 2009.
- [31] G. M. Nielson, " ν -quaternion splines for the smooth interpolation of orientations," *IEEE transactions on visualization and computer graphics*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 224–229, 2004.
- [32] T. Parcollet, M. Morchid, and G. Linarès, "A survey of quaternion neural networks," *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 53, pp. 2957–2982, 2020.
- [33] L. Lu, X. Zhang, and X. Xu, "Hypercomplex extreme learning machine with its application in multispectral palmprint recognition," *PloS one*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. e0209083, 2019.
- [34] Y. Zhou, L. Jin, H. Liu, and E. Song, "Color facial expression recognition by quaternion convolutional neural network with gabor attention," *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive and Developmental Systems*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 969–983, 2020.
- [35] J. Pöppelbaum and A. Schwung, "Predicting rigid body dynamics using dual quaternion recurrent neural networks with quaternion attention," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 82 923–82 943, 2022.
- [36] E. Bayro-Corrochano, "A survey on quaternion algebra and geometric algebra applications in engineering and computer science 1995–2020," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 104 326–104 355, 2021.
- [37] E. Bayro-Corrochano, E. Vazquez-Santacruz, E. Moya-Sanchez, and E. Castillo-Muñis, "Geometric bioinspired networks for recognition of 2-d and 3-d low-level structures and transformations," *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems*, vol. 27, no. 10, pp. 2020–2034, 2015.
- [38] E. Hitzer, C. Lator, and D. Hildenbrand, "Current survey of clifford geometric algebra applications," *Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences*, 2022.
- [39] T. Mizoguchi and I. Yamada, "Hypercomplex tensor completion via convex optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 67, no. 15, pp. 4078–4092, 2019.

- [40] Z. Xia, X. Wang, W. Zhou, R. Li, C. Wang, and C. Zhang, "Color medical image lossless watermarking using chaotic system and accurate quaternion polar harmonic transforms," *Signal Processing*, vol. 157, p. 108 – 118, 2019.